

Visual Simulation of Motion and Force Analysis of the Gear Linkage Mechanism

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There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The visualized input of geared linkage mechanism and visualization simulation on structural decomposition, kinematics and force analysis were mainly studied in this dissertation based on basic composition of the mechanism and general type transformation theory. The geared linkage component was normally deteriorated by take over the idea and innovation of subject Oriented, right off the bat, the article and classes needed in examination stent of system were determinate. Dimensional modeling and motion pair definition system, which realizes the visual input of the mechanism and the automatic identification of the structure information of the mechanism and the automation of structural decomposition. According to the analysis algorithm of type transformation method movement and force analysis, the mechanism movement analysis and / J points W baron automation. The dynamic simulation of the mechanism is realized in combination with the drawn mechanism I. Through the visual interface phantom drawing (including modification), input of simulation system parameters, dynamic simulation of mechanism, motion and force parameters of mechanism. The simulation graphics output is set in different windows on the same screen, so that users can simultaneously view from different levels: data, graphics wait to observe the operation of the organization. The model and unequivocal arrangement of the change primary investigation unit of the gear link mechanism are given, and the force of the gear-link mechanism is improved.

Keywords: VISUAL SIMULATION, OBJECT-ORIENTED TRANSFORMATION, MOTION ANALYSIS, FORCE ANALYSIS

1. Introduction

In the past two decades, the gear linkage mechanism (GLM) has been widely used. Its operation dynamic and force analysis is an important research content. Many scholars at home and abroad have carried out the gear linkage mechanism based on the research, there are four main methods in kinematic analysis: The complex vector method "", Group motion analysis method. ", The general analytical method." and The generalized transformation method "".... The first three are needles Establishing a mathematical model for each mechanism, and then using a certain mathematical method to solve it, not only does not have universal and the solution is more complicated. Such as G. N. Sander ""Using the complex number vector method to North American Academic Research, 4(12) | December 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5862024> | Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 112

analyze several common GIII conducted a comprehensive analysis of sports. The disadvantage of this method is that it needs to establish a set of non-linear equations are cumbersome to solve and the method is not universal. Hong Duli "", Zhu Youmin"". "To GLM The group motion analysis was studied, and several common organization group motion analysis numbers were established learn the model, and use the method of nonlinear equations to solve the motion, which can solve some GLM motion analysis problems, but several component groups listed in the article are not the most basic introduction. It is impossible to list all the component groups, so there are still a large number of GLM motion analysis problems.Can be resolved. Ye Zhonghe. "Called deletion proposed the "low-generation, one disassembly and one reduction method",utilizing this strategy to change over GLM dismantled into the interfacing connecting rods and stuff associating rods bunch comparing to the Assur bunch, they are relating to the Assur The essential connecting rods gathering these bar bunches have II stuff associating rods gathering, and there are linkage gear mechanism rods above grade III.This method requires motion analysis for each level II group and advanced group, and the types of the advanced group.It is impossible to list all types, so this method is still not universal, and it is difficult to realize automatically on a compute

2. Literature review

Regarding the research on the force analysis of GLM, in addition to the literature. Incidental, human-PC collaboration abilities are relatively poor, the connection point isn't cordial, and it is inopportune to utilize. In addition, the literature has the economic transformation theory and the general transformation theory are based on the object-oriented Visual C++ 5.0.Developed a set of visual input and structure decomposition, motion analysis and force analysis of the planar linkage mechanism the automatic solution and visualization of motion simulation software solves the above problems well .Currently, MDI's ADAMS software is a mechanical system.The leading software for motion and force analysis and simulation, it is a three dimensional solid modeling simulation software, using this this software can build and analyze the functional virtual prototype of the complex mechanical system, which is real on the computer.Ground simulation of all the motion characteristics of the mechanical system, but it is difficult to model in this software system.The interface of this system is also relatively complicated, it is not convenient to use, and it is not suitable for general engineering and technical personnel.In short, foreign software is better in human-computer interaction, graphics and image processing and visualization.There is nothing that can be done. Like the Working Model, for a slightly more complex mechanism, its analysis speed,it is slower, and constraint loading failure will occur during assembly, which will eventually lead to assembly failure. Domestic institutions although the analysis software has been used in mechanism motion analysis and force analysis methods and general procedures.Reach the world's advanced level, but in the combination of product kinematics and dynamics analysis of mechanical products, excellent computer simulation, human-computer interaction, graphics and image processing, and visualization are in line with international advanced.

2.1 The main work of this paper

The main work of this paper is as follows:

1. According to the composition principle of the gear linkage mechanism of the generalized transformation method, object-oriented thinking is adopted. I want to use technology to decompose a gear-link mechanism naturally in the problem area, and determine what needs to be used. Objects and classes: establish appropriate class levels to complete the object-oriented analysis and design of the entire software system design, establish a reasonable data structure.

2. No development of the two-dimensional intelligent modeling system of the mechanism, especially the gear-related components and hydraulic pressure two-dimensional modeling of components and extraction and simulation of motion parameters. This paper has developed a set of institutional intelligence two three-dimensional modeling and motion pair definition system to realize an interactive drawing of two-dimensional entity modeling of the mechanism on the microcomputer. Figure, the computer automatically recognizes the figure (recording component and movement characteristics), and then compiles it with C++. The program extracts data from components and kinematic sub-features. And automatically analyze the topology, and finally the structure analysis result is given in the form of a dialog box to realize the possibility of using the type conversion method to decompose the structure of the organization visual simulation.

3. This article studies the power analysis of GLM and gives the GLM-type transformation mana analysis unit the model and mathematical analytic formula of, perfect the mathematical model of GLM force analysis, and combine the mechanism graphics and the structure decomposition route is based on the analysis algorithm of motion analysis and force analysis according to the use type conversion method to realize automation of mechanism motion analysis and force analysis.

4. Using the method of movement inversion and movement transformation, the active part is realized as a non-connecting rod in the program the movement analysis of the plane linkage mechanism in the calculation method of dynamic analysis. This method is used in the program to realize the linear drive of the planar linkage mechanism perform motion analysis.

3 Basic theory

3.1 Introduction to the theory of transformation and generalized transformation

As of late, a lot of investigation has been done on the work of PC helped gear linkage system at home and abroad, no similar insightful strategies utilize various standards, yet the fundamental thought is to stall the body as indicated by a specific law a progression of essential units, the unit is broke down, in the requirement connection between the units to get the body by and large examination. The institutional arrangement of the previous Soviet researcher Assour's institutional structure is: foundations: racks and unique moving parts and pole gatherings. go through this deterioration, the investigation of the construction turns into the examination of the bar bunch, according to the primary perspective, the bar bunch is clear more straightforward than the establishment it comprises of, so this hypothesis significantly streamlines institutional analysis; since the bar bunch is a unit with no levels of opportunity, the unit has the sureness of movement and power, so the pole bunches at everything levels can be dissected ahead of time, and when the particular components are broke down, the decay request can be founded on them to conjure the out-of-the-case arrangement of the bar bunch disintegrated by this system, hence making the examination of the

instrument quicker and simpler. However, because of the assortment of Asur bar gatherings, complex design structure, just the optional pole gathering can be shown arrangement, for pole bunches over three levels, the goal is a supernatural condition with three-sided capacities, which is additionally required address it alliteratively

In any case, in the particular use of the kind change strategy, particularly the power investigation, it is observed that the power examination can not be caused the change of type and movement examination to have arrived at the solidarity, and the writing has embraced the embodiment of the hypothesis of type change further inside and out conversation, set forward an expansive transformation hypothesis: that is, in the rod bunch by putting various inner parasor The number is changed over to an outer sub-boundary (for example virtual) without the need to unconstrained, subsequently empowering the pole gathering to be changed over virtual single-part, compelled single-part, and two-rod groups

That is: the mechanism of the rack and $+\sum$ original moving parts and $+\sum$ virtual single the components, $+\sum$ the two-rod group and the $+\sum$ constraint single component, make the transformation theory more perfect and more conducive to the establishment of the machine a unified mathematical model and system method for structural, kinetic and kinetic analysis, and it is easy to realize automation of computer-aided analysis.

3.2 GLM's generalized transformation basic unit

The most significant advantage of GLM generalized transformation is to decompose complex mechanisms into the simplest, with certainty explicit solution, the least type of three basic units of transformation: virtual single component, generalized double-bar group, constrain single components, and various types of units have different types and arrangement orders of their constituent units. Different kinds. The unit collection of GLM not only includes all the units of the planar linkage mechanism, but also has its own unique unit type. The unique component in GLM is a component containing gear pairs, namely teeth there are three types of wheel CC, wheel rod fixing part CL, and rack PL, so the unique unit type of GLM can be Obtained by the type of component. Explicit solution, the least type of three basic units of transformation: virtual single component, generalized double-bar group, constrain the single component, and various types of units have different types and arrangement orders of the sub-units. Different kinds. The unit collection of GLM not only includes all the units of the planar linkage mechanism, but also has its own unique unit type. The unique component in GLM is the component containing gear pair, namely the tooth. There are three types of wheel CC, wheel rod fixing part CL, and rack PL, so the unique unit type of GLM can be obtained by the type of component.

(1) Vice Elements

There are five types of vice elements: rotating vice element R, moving vice element S and G, and gear vice element Ge. And rack vice element Re. (As shown in Figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1 Schematic outline of the kinds of auxiliary components

(2) Single component

The generalized conversion standard single component is always considered to be composed of one rod and two pairs, virtual single component and constraint.

The types of single components are as follows:

Virtual single component: RRIM RSIM RGIM SRIM SSIM SGIM GRIM GSIM GGIM CRIM CSIM CGIM CCIM RCIM

Constraint single component: RRCT RSCT RGCT SRCT SScT SGCT GRCT GSCT GGCT

(3) Two-rod group

The generalized conversion standard double-stroke group is always considered to be composed of two strokes and three pairs, and there are 23 types: RRRR RRRS RRRG RSGR RSGS RSGG RGSR RGSB RGSS SRRR SRRS SRRG SSGR SGSR GRRR GRRS GSGR GRRG GGSR CCCC CLCL CTPL PLCL

Due to the existence of senior mates in GLM, there is a special contract bundle unit, it is composed of three components and three auxiliary elements, this kind of about "L" the type of beam unit is CCCT (as shown in Figure(3-2)).

Figure (3-2) CCCT constraint unit

The definition of the identification pair of the unit without gear components above is the same as that of reference [3], including gear components. The sub-instructions for the identification of the unit are as follows:

CL→The component type of the first component n1

PL→The component type of the second component n2

Figure (3-3) An example of a double-bar group identifier

The double-bar group unit corresponding to the above double-bar group identification pair is shown in Figure 3-3.

3.3 Type of transformation principle of GLM

Suppose anatomical structure gear linkage mechanism is fl: number is n, the number of motion pairs is Ill, and its three-color topological graph G is

The primary amount of loops is:

$$L = m - n + 1 \quad (3-1)$$

There are 2^L elements in the loop space S(G) of this graph, as long as the 4 and the set of S(G) are the most common.

Get all the four circuits of this figure. Using these three circuits, you can establish the equations:

$$F(\varphi) = (f_1(\varphi_1), \psi_1(\varphi_1), f_2(\varphi_2), \psi_2(\varphi_2), \dots, f_{L_t}(\varphi_{L_t}), \psi_{L_t}(\varphi_{L_t})) = 0 \quad (3-2)$$

Secondary coordinate collection $f_1(\varphi_1), \psi_1(\varphi_1)$ is a pair of constraint equations established by the j loop.

$$\varphi_{Nj} = \varphi_1 U \varphi_2 U \dots \varphi_{j-1} \quad (j = 2, \dots, L_t) \quad (3-3)$$

$$\varphi_{N1} = \varphi$$

In the formula φ_{Nj} , middle. Represents the known set of secondary coordinates when calculating the m_j loop; j is an empty set.

$$m_j = \text{degree}[\varphi_j - (\varphi_{Nj} \cap \varphi_j)] - c_1 \quad (j=1 - L_t) \quad (3-4)$$

$$P_{mj} = \begin{cases} m_j & (m_j > 0) \\ 0 & (m_j \leq 0) \end{cases} \quad (3-5)$$

The result of enhancement and arranging limits the arrangement of conditions M. In this way, the system of equations is solved sequential., The equation finds the value, furthermore the other M conditions will be utilized as viable conditions to change the principal M virtual boundary variables, until the viable conditions

are totally settled, the center right now is the arrangement of the situation and the genuine place of the component as of now.

(a) Organization diagram

(b) Structural decomposition route

(b) Weighted three-color diagram

The organization shown in Figure 2-4(a), $n=5$, $m=6$, $L=6-5+1=2$, $Lr=\{L_{12345}, L_{345}\}$:

Secondary coordinates $\varphi = \varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4, S_e$, Here S_e The phase caused by high deputy e The secondary coordinate of the tangential displacement. Optimizing and sorting a set of independent the basic loop L_{12345}, L_{345} and select component 5 as the computing machine frame, establish the following equation

$$\begin{cases} f_1(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3) = 0 \\ \Psi_1(\varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4) = 0 \\ f_1(\varphi_3, \varphi_4, S_e) = 0 \\ \Psi_2(\varphi_3, \varphi_4, S_e) = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\Phi_{h1} = \{\varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4\} \quad \Phi_{b2} = \{\varphi_3, \varphi_4, S_e\}$$

$$\Phi_{N1} = \varphi \quad \Phi_{N2} = \Phi_{b1} = \{\varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4\}$$

$$m_1 = degree[\Phi_{b1} - (\Phi_{N1} \cap \Phi_{b1})] - 2 = degree[\{\varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4\} - 2] = 3 - 2 = 1$$

$$m_2 = degree[\Phi_{b1} - (\Phi_{N2} \cap \Phi_{b2})] - 2 = degree[\{\varphi_3, \varphi_4, S_e\} - \{\varphi_3, \varphi_4\}] = 3 - 2 - 2 = -1$$

$$P_{m1} = 1 \quad P_{m2} = 0$$

$$M = P_{m1} + P_{m2} = 1$$

Feed the process of solving the above equations into the motion analysis of the mechanism, that is, the type transformation method. In the process of analyzing the position of the mechanism, M is the type transformation number, and m is defined as the degree of freedom of the loop-matter. The theoretical meaning is the mobility of circuit j relative to the computing frame in the process of mechanism transformation.

3.4 The principle of type transformation analysis and the reversible feeding of sports analysis

3.4.1 Principles of Type Transformation Analysis

When using the type conversion method to analyze the movement of the gear connection f...: group, the movement parameters of the outer pair of the rod group for your own knowledge, the motion parameters of the inner pair are to be determined. The force analysis of the gear connecting rod group is very similar to the motion analysis. The big difference is that the internal and external motion force parameters in the rod group are both unknown, and the known conditions only act on the external force, external force couple, gravity, inertial force and inertial couple on the mechanism. According to the definition of the rod group, the rod group is a unit with zero degrees of freedom, so any gear connected the rod and rod groups all satisfy the formula:

$$3n - 2p - P_H = 0 \quad (2-6)$$

n → The number of components that make up the rod group

P → The number of low pairs that make up the pole group

P_H → The number of high pairs that make up the pole group

This recipe not just shows the determinism of the gear linkage bunch, yet additionally clarifies the gear linkage. The conviction of the static power of the rod group, that is: every part can list three free power balance conditions, each the low pair has two parts in the X and y direction which are obscure, and each gear high pair has just a single autonomous part. If the force is unknown, then $(2p + P_n)$ unknown forces can be solved by $3n$ balance equations. When performing force analysis on GLM, there is also a type conversion problem, if there are $(2p + P_n)$ constraint reaction forces. In the virtual one or several force components are known, set as m (that is, the type transformation number of GLM), then the force balance condition of the rod group is transformed, it was originally $(2p + P_n)$ an unmapped force, now the number becomes $(2p + P_n - m)$. In this way, the rod group as a whole system loses its balance, therefore, m additional balance forces or balance moments are required in the system to obtain a new level of balance for this system. The number of unknown forces is restored to $(2p + pl)$.

As shown in Figures 2 – 5, the members 2 and 3 are virtual units on which the tangential force F of the high pair is virtual. For already knowing; member 1 is a restraining unit, and a balance moment M needs to be attached to it to be balanced. When

$m_j = 0$, When, When, F_t is the true value.

Figure 3-5 Force analysis route

3.4.2 The changeability form of transformation synthesis and movement analysis

Since the kind of change examination and the development investigation are both bound together the N recipe, the power investigation and the movement examination is decayed into virtual single part, summed up twofold pole bunch, and obliged single part through type change. Then they must have an inherent mutual relationship. After research, it is found that the gear connecting rod group is the same as the plane connecting rod group... [3], and its force analysis and operation dynamic analysis has unity and reciprocity. In immediate transformation, the number of transformations between force analysis and motion analysis M can be equal, and the calculation process of force analysis and motion analysis are mutually inverse. Force analysis and movement points. The reciprocity of analysis means that the structural decomposition route of force analysis and the structural decomposition route of motion analysis can be inverse, that is, the virtual unit of force analysis is the constraint unit of motion analysis, and the virtual unit of motion analysis element is the constraint unit of force analysis. Figure 2-6 shows the motion analysis path of the rod group shown in Figure 2-5.

Figure 2—6 Motion analysis route

4 GLM visual input and organization recognition and structure analysis solution realization

Institutional structure, which mainly reveals the regularity of the structure of the institution and the characteristics of the topological structure of the institution and the internal connection with the characteristics of kinematics and dynamics. The establishment of a unified mathematical model of mechanics and system theory provides a basic basis. In-type transformation law institutions. In the analysis, the structural analysis of the organization is mainly the automatic generation of the decomposition route of the organization. The line provides the division mode of the unit for the mechanism motion and dynamic analysis; the positive sequence of the structural decomposition route is used J two motion analysis, the reverse order will be used for force analysis, so as to establish mechanism structure analysis and motion analysis unified mathematical a model with force analysis.

4.1 The use of item arranged innovation in the improvement of the construction graph subsystem

In reality, a complex figure is made out of numerous basic figures, and a complex the system chart of is made out of different basic parts and the movement sets of interfacing parts. This hypothesis and current the rules from simple to complex in the real world coincide. Therefore, when constructing the mechanism graphics system. Its basic idea is: use simpler. A single component and kinematic pair graphics are used to construct complex mechanism graphics. The document [3] has already given the mechanism graphical hierarchy model. Object-oriented technology is suitable for the construction of the graphic hierarchy of institutions. The graphic reality we are investigating In essence, it is the unity of data and function, and is the basic unit of our processing. According to this point of view, The interactive graphics we are studying has always been object-oriented, which means it's all about It is not difficult to understand the representation and operation of graphical objects.

4.2 Design of the Graphical Subsystem of the Diagram of Intelligent Mechanism

From the above analysis, it can be seen that an organization graphic object is a combination of multiple component graphic objects gather. According to the shape of the component, the component graphics can be divided into: rectangle, polygon, circle, rectangle. The combined shape with the circle and the combination of rectangle and rectangle; according to the shape of the sports pair, the sports pair can be divided into: rotating pair, fixed rotating pair, sliding pair (S pair and G pair), gear pair (G. Pair and R.vice). From the object-oriented thinking, every --*l'graphic object should be designed with a new class to manage he drawing, access, and modification of management objects, as graphic objects have some common attributes and methods, So it makes sense to construct a graphics base class (Cchartobj). Such common attributes and the method can be defined in the base class, and the new derived class only needs to add its own specific implementation and methods.

So; the most important point is that by defining a virtual function in the base class, the runtime of the reference the polymorphism mechanism will bring convenience to the future program function expansion: and the establishment of this type of system. Full consideration is given to the convenience of structural information identification of the organization chart and dynamic simulation of the organization. Department of Institutional Graphics the system structure of the system class is as follows (only the newly added component graphics classes in GLM are listed here).

5 The driving part is a non-connecting rod connected with a linear drive plane motion analysis of lever mechanism

Literature [3] uses an object-oriented method to visualize the movement and force analysis of the planar linkage mechanism. The simulation has been studied, but this analysis software did not realize that the active parts are non-linked rods and linear drives. Kinematic analysis of moving planar linkage mechanism. As mentioned in the previous analysis of the movement and force of the unit, GLM contains a plane link. The types of all units in the mechanism, so both the GLM motion and force analysis visual simulation program the motion and force of the planar linkage can also be analyzed. In order to perfect the planar linkage mechanism Kinematic analysis, this article analyzes the movement of the non-linking rod and the linearly driven planar linkage mechanism as the active part. The analysis was conducted.

5.1 Kinematics Analysis of Planar Linkage Mechanism with Non-linking Frame as the Active Part

In the plane linkage mechanism, most of its active parts are linkage rods, but there are exceptions, including hydraulic and pneumatic. The plane link mechanism of the component (referred to as the hydro-pneumatic plane link mechanism) is a typical active part. The plane linkage mechanism of the linkage rod, as shown in Figure 5-1 (a), is widely used in engineering. In addition, the planar linkage system of the two IF linkage bars likewise incorporates a non-hydraulic pneumatic planar linkage instrument, as displayed in Figure 5-1(b) Machine shown

(a) Hydro-pneumatic plane linkage mechanism

(b) Non-hydraulic pneumatic plane linkage mechanism

Figure 5-1 Plane linkage mechanism with a non-linkage rod

As displayed in Figure 5-2, the xoy coordinate framework is fixed on the first instrument outline, and the x'o'y' coordinate framework is fixed set on the new (later the development is reversed) reference part, the M point is any point on the system, at x'. "center. The coordinates are ($\hat{x}$, y), the coordinates in xoy are ($\mathcal{X}$, Y), and AB is a direction on the frame of the original mechanism line segment (it can be represented by two lines on the rack), the coordinate of point A in x'o'y' is ($x_{1f}y_{1f}$), the inclination angle of AB in θ_{1f} is roar, and the inclination angle in x'o'y' is θ_{0f} .

Figure 5-2

From the above value, the inclination angle of ox relative to $o'x'$ can be obtained θ .

$$\theta = \theta_{1i} - \theta_{1f} \quad (5-1)$$

Coordinate transformation is actually to use the coordinates in xoy to represent the coordinates of any point on the mechanism. The calculation expression is as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 - x_{0f} \\ y_1 - y_{0f} \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & \sin\theta \\ -\sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{cases} x_{1i} - x_{1f} \\ y_{1i} - y_{1f} \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = (x_{1i} - x_{0f}) \cdot \cos\theta + (y_{1i} - y_{1f}) \cdot \sin\theta + x_{0f} \\ y_1 = (y_{1i} - y_{1f}) \cdot \cos\theta - (x_{1i} - x_{1f}) \cdot \sin\theta + y_{0f} \end{cases}$$

Respectively carry on the first and second time to the formula (5-2), find the derivative, and get the following speed

$$\begin{cases} x_1 - x_{0f} \\ y_1 - y_{0f} \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & \sin\theta \\ -\sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{cases} x_{1i} - x_{1f} \\ y_{1i} - y_{1f} \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = (x_{1i} - x_{0f}) \cdot \cos\theta + (y_{1i} - y_{1f}) \cdot \sin\theta + x_{0f} \\ y_1 = (y_{1i} - y_{1f}) \cdot \cos\theta - (x_{1i} - x_{1f}) \cdot \sin\theta + y_{0f} \end{cases} \quad (5-2)$$

As mentioned earlier, if the active part is a non-linking rod, the motion analysis of the planar linkage mechanism is not used. The dynamic inversion method for analysis and calculation may increase, so two kinds of analysis procedures are adopted. Analysis method, that is, the general analysis method (using the first loop to analyze through the frame) and the motion inversion set analysis method (using the first loop to analyze without passing through the rack).

5.2 Motion analysis of linear drive planar linkage mechanism

The so-called linear drive means that the movement of the active part is linear movement. This sort of planar linkage component a normal model is the hydro-pneumatic plane linkage instrument, writing for straight drive

level the kinematic investigation of the surface linkage system has been talked about partially, however the sorts they examined are not finished and the technique utilized isn't widespread, and it is hard to apply to all inclusive examination programming. This article will the method is extended to the analysis of the type conversion method, and the linear drive plane linkage mechanism is realized in the program motion analysis. Because there is a liquid-gas drive in the mechanism, and these liquid-pneumatic components are active parts after structural decomposition, they will exist in some units. We can imagine One of the components in the type conversion unit of the planar linkage mechanism described in is converted into a hydro-pneumatic component, and it becomes a type conversion unit containing active components. These units containing the original moving parts, we call them active equivalent unit.

If the active components and active pairs in the active equivalent unit are connected in series on the unit chain, these units will be It is not possible to directly use the existing analytical formulae of the element without hydro-pneumatic components to solve the calculation. However, we can use their composition rules to find out that this type of unit is suitable for computer programming and simplified calculations general algorithm.

1 Analysis of of dynamic comparable virtual single part unit

Figure 5-3 The general form of active equivalent virtual single-component unit

Since the development of the dynamic part and its moving partner is relative, the dynamic part can be generally the development of the contrary part is changed into the development of the contrary piece of the dynamic part comparative with the dynamic part, so the upper the kinematic chain displayed in the figure is changed into the identical kinematic chain displayed in Fig. 4-4, so the overall development is changed from organize in the rods course n and vice course

Figure 5-4 The comparable kinematic chain of the dynamic identical virtual single-part unit

The change of the phase sequence motion variable is:

$$u = -v$$

Later the above change, virtual a movement boundary on the (rod 1) where is found, then, at that point, the development boundaries of this rod not set in stone, and the general development of rod 1 and rod 2 is known, so the rod can be determined 2 The movement boundaries under this virtual variable can at last be

determined for the sub-movement under this virtual variable boundaries, it additionally finishes the investigation of the dynamic comparable virtual single-part unit.

2 Analysis of active equivalent double rod group

In the process of structural decomposition, we "rigidize" the active part to its moving counterpart. In this way, the decomposition form of the active equivalent double rod group is the same as the passive double rod group unit mentioned above. Indeed, in the removal examination, we can likewise utilize these dynamic comparable two fold rod groups with a similar sort of aloof two fold the rod groups (here called the same unit of the dynamic identical twofold rod groups) is determined by the insightful equation, however right now the underlying boundaries of the same unit (here called the same boundary, which is identical to the information part of the latent unit) It is not constant, but needs to be calculated for each position. A calculation will be introduced below these equivalent parameters and the general algorithm for solving the position parameters of the active equivalent double-rod group element.

Figure 5-5 The overall type of the dynamic comparable double rod group

- ① Give $l_{1,2}$. The pole has a dummy position parameter value port, the selection of the target parameter is determined according to the type of dummy variable of RSIM, so that it can be determined certainly,. A virtual position of the rod.
- ② relative position $l_{1,2}$ of the rod is known, so it can be the order is determined $l_{1,2}$ the position parameter of the lever at this time, so that the dummy position parameter of n_3 pair can be obtained.

Final result

The main work done in this paper and the main results obtained are as follows:

1. Through the examination of the GLM arrangement and the essential standards of GLM investigation dependent on the summed up change strategy the item situated examination technique is utilized to set up the article model of GLM investigation by type change strategy, and the plan the items and classes that should be utilized are set up; a sensible information structure is set up, and the article situated C++ language is utilized the language executes the meaning, everything being equal.
2. From an object-oriented point of view, the GLM graphics hierarchy model is proposed. Full advantage using object-oriented inheritance, polymorphic and other mechanisms, the system structure of the institutional graphics system is established and a reasonable data structure, the graphic selection, rotation, and stretching of

the component diagram with gears are given and other operation methods, and developed a set of intelligent two-dimensional modeling and motion pair definition system of the mechanism. Realize the interactive drawing of the two-dimensional entity modeling diagram of the mechanism on the microcomputer.

3. This article realizes the automatic recognition of graphics by the computer (recording the characteristics of each component and movement pair) and automatically analyze the topological structure, and finally give the structure analysis result in the form of a dialog box to realize visualization of the structural analysis of the transformation method.

4. This article combines the research of GLM force analysis in the literature [4], and perfects the mathematical model of GLM force analysis. Type, gives the mathematical analytical formula of the GLM force analysis conversion unit.

5. Combine the mechanism graphics and structure decomposition route in 2 to move according to the usage transformation method the analysis algorithm of analysis and force analysis realizes the automation of mechanism motion analysis and force analysis.

Conclusion:

Through the visual interface, the drawing of mechanism graphics (including modification), the adjustment of simulation system parameters, and the dynamic simulation of structure motion, the simulation graphics output of mechanism motion and force parameters are concentrated on the same screen. The same window allows users to observe the movement of the mechanism from different levels, data, graphics, etc. at the same time condition. After the mechanism parameters are modified, it can automatically deform and continue to calculate and display. When inputting data, half of the input can be saved, and then continue to input after opening, and pass. However, due to time constraints, the software developed in this article is still inadequate improve and perfect.

The main deficiencies are as follows:

The scope of use of this software is limited, and it has not been implemented to

Analyze complex GLM such as gears and triple gears, and use non-connecting rods for linear drives and active parts Force analysis of the plane linkage mechanism. The fault tolerance and interaction capabilities of the program are limited and need to be further improved. With the continuous improvement of computer hardware, the degree of visualization in institutional analysis needs to be improved.

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